

MODERN ORGANIZATIONAL FORMS IN TEACHING MUSIC THEORETICAL DISCIPLINES

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The modern musical and pedagogical process is an integral system of interacting structural units, where each is a specific block of organizational, informational, educational, scientific practical, methodical and creative activities.

The effectiveness of the functioning of teaching music-theoretical disciplines, first of all, depends on the skillful organization of the educational “organism”, in which objective and subjective factors are involved, but the organizational talent of the teacher, who must master all modern forms of education, is fundamental.

The musical-theoretical block of disciplines has the following forms of education: group, small-group and individual. The most common and effective - small-group. Organization in such groups is carried out taking into account the quantitative composition - at least two and no more eight people, the smaller the composition, the wider the opportunities for the teacher to freely implement their ideas, pedagogical goals, tasks, for the solution of which both academic and modern teaching aids are involved. At the same time, the palette of organizational activity among students also increases. They get more independence in the choice of teaching methods, which contributes to the expansion of their horizons, increases the desire for perfection, which is very important for the development of young musicians. The qualitative composition of the group is the level of knowledge of the trainees. Unfortunately, when organizing groups, this factor is taken into account extremely rarely. It is pedagogically justified if a small group is planned to be single-level in terms of its qualitative composition (medium, high level of knowledge). In such a group, the psychological and pedagogical influence gives more mutual understanding, and pedagogical guidance gives rise to positive emotions and purposefully leads to effective training in the musical- theoretical cycle.

The teacher should organize training taking into account modern requirements and interests of the individual, including such types of work as trainings, debates, quizzes, interactive teaching methods, so that focus their students only on positive results, inspire them with a sense of confidence, while fulfilling the basic requirements of modern pedagogy:

1. *Goodwill*
2. *Correctness*

3. *Patience*
4. *Take into account the wishes of students*
5. *Demandingness*
6. *Eliminate the negative of premature characteristics*
7. *Argument your decisions*

After determining the actions to create groups, one should proceed to a practical organizational form - the definition of specific knowledge and skills in the disciplines of teaching (harmony, solfeggio, music theory, polyphony). It is desirable to carry out practical organization from the first lessons in writing (testing, written exercises, tasks), oral (interviews, disputes, questionnaires), preferably and comprehensively, in order to obtain more objective results. To do this, it is necessary to define evaluation criteria. These include:

- 1) *Theoretical knowledge*
- 2) *Practical skills (playing the piano)*
- 3) *Analytical capabilities*
- 4) *Creativity*
- 5) *Possession of modern forms and methods of work (computer technology)*
- 6) *Good musical memory*

Of course, the proposed criteria can be changed, enriched at the discretion of the teacher, but thanks to them it is possible to determine the real level of preparedness of the group, which will allow proceeding to the next organizational form - writing a program in the discipline under study and taking into account the knowledge of this audience. The program should reflect all the structures of the taught discipline (subject content, language of instruction, types of control, the number of hours allocated for training by semesters, basic and recommended literature).

It follows from the foregoing that modern organizational forms teaching music-theoretical disciplines consist of:

1. Distribution of the audience into small groups
2. Determining the knowledge of students
3. Writing a program for the discipline, for a specific group
4. Teaching the discipline, taking into account the choice of language
5. Definition, creation and inclusion in the pedagogical process of modern, interactive teaching methods
6. Control of students' knowledge, based on program requirements for subject matter throughout the course.

7. Accounting and encouragement of students who have shown special diligence, creative activity, excellence in learning, who are able to argue and defend your position on this issue.

We believe that the interaction of modern forms of organization of education with the obligatory consideration of the psychological and pedagogical factor in the chain "teacher - student - teacher", where the teacher acts as a carrier of knowledge, a benevolent organizer who manages the entire learning process, allows you to ensure a high level in mastering musical theoretical disciplines.

The proposed modern forms of organization of education are used in the pedagogical activity of the teacher Evgenia Veziryan at the Republican Secondary Special Musical School named after. V. Uspensky

